

Substrate-film interfacial interaction in the fabrication of ZnO photocatalytic thin films via sol-gel and aqueous solution-gel CSD processing

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ABSTRACT

Despite the many environmental advantages that Chemical Solution Deposition (CSD) processes can offer for the production of thin films and functional coatings, their industrial adoption is still a long way off. Inconveniences related to the lack of homogeneity and, occasionally, poor microstructural control, can ultimately complicate the achievement of uniform deposits with reproducible properties. A key factor is the interaction at the substrate-film interface. In addition to compositional differences, other structural and microstructural properties of the substrate such as its crystallinity, crystalline orientation, and surface roughness, can be crucial in successfully replacing the energy-intensive processes commonly used to produce functional films with more sustainable processing alternatives. This study investigates the potential of two simple CSD procedures—the well-known sol-gel method and an inspired variant in a fully aqueous medium (aqueous solution-gel)—for the sustainable fabrication of ZnO thin films with photocatalytic properties. The semiconductor coatings are deposited on a variety of substrates, including amorphous and crystalline silica, a high roughness alumina, and a conductive platinum-based material, aiming to assess the impact of substrate properties on photocatalytic performance while evaluating the effectiveness of both methods for producing functional thin films. The findings reveal the challenges of achieving uniform coverage on highly irregular surfaces, but also demonstrate that both techniques are very versatile and hold promise for future large-scale thin film applications.

1. Introduction

The production of ZnO thin films has been the subject of intense research for many years, as it is very likely that the excellent physicochemical properties of this wide bandgap ceramic semiconductor can be magnified or even expanded in the film geometry. As distinguishing features, zinc oxide films exhibit high exciton binding energy, high electron mobility, sizeable piezo-optic and piezoelectric properties, and a relatively high optical transparency over the entire visible spectral

range [1]. ZnO coatings and films thus find application in multiple technological fields, including different types of optoelectronic devices, solar cells and self-cleaning coatings, thin film transistors and piezoelectric transducers, biosensors and biomedical implants, surface acoustic wave devices, etc. [2–9]. Their application has also been extended to the photocatalytic removal of pollutants from aqueous media, offer an environmentally friendly and sustainable way to purify water which uses light to break down harmful chemicals into innocuous substances [10,11]. This interest is linked to the adoption of effective

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manufacturing methods for ZnO thin films, and in this search different strategies have been put into practice, ranging from sophisticated vapour deposition methodologies to soft solution-based deposition processes. Physical and chemical vapour deposition techniques (PLD, MBE, sputtering, MOCVD, etc.) allow for uniform and homogeneous deposits with exceptional conformal coverage [12,13]. They also provide a high degree of compositional and structural control at the atomic level, which can lead to the growth of high-quality films in terms of texture, thickness, crystallographic orientation, microstructure and interface matching (interaction with the substrate) [14]. These techniques are the most common at industrial level but they are not without limitations: on the one hand, the high energy consumption involved in terms of vacuum and/or temperature is in itself an environmental issue that also restricts the range of materials to which they can be applied; on the other hand, the aforementioned high degree of sophistication increases equipment costs and leads to scaling up difficulties. In contrast, solution based deposition methods (usually labelled CSD, Chemical Solution Deposition) may initially not offer the same level of control over film properties and microstructure, for example making epitaxial growth relatively complicated, but still provide excellent control of stoichiometry and coverage of large surface areas [15]; actually, the microstructure of solution-derived films is usually controlled by kinetic factors rather than by thermodynamic ones, meaning that by suitably manipulating the processing conditions it is possible to gain increased control over the film growth process. This makes CSD processes very versatile, but their main advantage is undoubtedly the low energy consumption and low investment costs, as they do not require intense vacuum technology or complicated reactors [16,17]. However, CSD techniques are less frequently employed in industry due to problems related to the homogeneity of the obtained coatings; for example, even in situations of precise control over the solution and deposition conditions, the preferential growth of the nuclei over the formation of new nuclei may result in the appearance of dots, clusters or islands, ultimately complicating the obtaining of uniform films [18]. In this context, the question arises to what extent CSD methods can replace vapour deposition processes to obtain thin film materials and devices in a more sustainable way and without entailing a significant loss of properties and performance. The answer to that question is not ubiquitous and is conditioned by both the type of material to be obtained (for a given application) and the variables involved in the particular CSD technique. Numerous research groups are working worldwide towards this goal and, in particular, we here focus on analysing the production of ZnO thin films by sol-gel based procedures. By far one of the most extensively studied CSD techniques, the sol-gel process can be well adapted to the production of ZnO thin films in a highly simple and controllable way [15,19–21]. In brief, the chemistry of the sol-gel process is based on a controlled sequence of hydrolysis and condensation reactions in which a colloidal suspension of the appropriate precursors (sol) is converted into a three dimensional cohesive network (gel). The commonly reported CSD precursor sols are prepared from alkoxides or acetates dissolved in alcoholic solvents. Film formation then proceeds by depositing the precursor sol on a substrate using a cost-effective coating approach such as spin- or dip-coating. The process ends with a subsequent annealing at mild to low temperatures to cause thermal decomposition of the gel and the crystallization (nucleation and growth) of the oxide material. Several parameters in the overall procedure can be revised and accordingly countless modifications have been worked out over the years, including different types of precursors, annealing temperatures or changes in the organic solvents [15,22,23]. A less explored alternative consists of using water as the only solvent in the recipe, turning the process into an aqueous solution-gel methodology. In the aqueous routine, precursor solutions are prepared from simple metal salts that are dissolved in water and stabilized against uncontrolled hydrolysis (and precipitation) by complexation with peroxy- and citrate-ligands that show strong electron donating functionalities [24]. The procedure meets the demands of any other chemical solution deposition route by

endorsing high homogeneity, compositional control and favourable thermal budget (low phase formation temperatures); compared to the alcoholic counterpart, it also implies a significant reduction of environmental and safety hazards while providing an easier to handle and less expensive option. The water-based deposition methodology has proven effective for the preparation of various electroceramic film compositions, although just a couple of publications have considered its application to the production of ZnO films [25–29]. A major obstacle is perhaps the poor affinity of the substrates for water. Actually, the choice of the substrate is sometimes taken for granted, but is one of the most important issues in the film growth process. At the interface between the substrate and the film, a complex interplay of chemical, physical and mechanical interactions takes place that greatly influences the film properties and performance. This includes the quality (homogeneity), structure and crystallinity (atomic ordering), and the functionality of the deposited film and, for example, in the specific case of ZnO thin films, the substrate can be crucial not only to provide sufficient adhesion but to increase the efficiency of their semiconductor specifications.

This work presents a systematic study on the preparation of ZnO thin films using sol-gel and aqueous solution-gel methods on various substrate types. The investigation primarily explores the film–substrate interfacial interactions and how these are strongly influenced by the processing history. Special emphasis is placed on the potential of the aqueous method—less explored in the literature—to enable epitaxial-like growth on selected substrates. While initially aimed at achieving a reproducible photocatalytic response, the findings also offer valuable insights into when and how chemical solution deposition (CSD) can serve as a practical and viable alternative to vapour-phase deposition techniques.

2. Experimental details

2.1. Substrate selection

Specific thin-film applications require different substrate materials that can offer an ideal compromise between providing mechanical support and proficient adhesion, and conceding/ensuring a customized functionality. Being an active area of research, in the particular case of zinc oxide films the lack of a reliably available homosubstrate motivates the use of dissimilar supports whose crystal structure allows some degree of lattice matching and thermal compatibility with the wurtzite-type structure of ZnO [30]. Up to four of them have been tested here for the two CSD processing protocols described below. On one hand, silicon oxide substrates were selected due to their potential to enable effective integration of ZnO-based devices with silicon-based integrated circuit technology [31]. Moreover, given that the lattice mismatch and crystallographic orientation of the substrate significantly influence the nucleation and growth mechanisms of ZnO thin films (for example facilitating heteroepitaxial alignment) both amorphous silica glass and single-crystalline (0001)-oriented SiO₂ substrates were investigated. Likewise, inexpensive and easily available Al₂O₃ substrates were analysed as they are broadly used in optoelectronic applications due to their ultra-wide band-gap, high thermal stability and chemical durability [32]; for this study, however, a high roughness alumina with no preferential orientation was chosen in order to elucidate to what extent CSD techniques allow conformal coverage when working with intricate (coarse) topographies. Finally, a platinum-based substrate was also examined, this being the common conductive choice in several electroceramic thin films studies due to its good chemical stability and low resistance [33,34]; moreover, earlier works using pulsed laser deposition methods pointed to a low in-plane misfit between the Pt (111) surface and the c-axis of ZnO [35,36], which shall facilitate obtaining a well-defined crystallographic orientation in the deposited films.

2.2. CSD processing

In addition to the specific role of the substrate, all other CSD variables influence the crystallization of the ZnO films, including solution chemistry, deposition technique, treatment conditions and growth time, etc. On this basis, we have selected a fixed set of experimental conditions that, according to specialized reviews on the topic [19,37], are reliably effective in producing dense and homogeneous coatings. Briefly, the main steps of the sol-gel and aqueous solution-gel processing protocols practiced here are summarized as follows: in the case of the sol-gel routine, hereafter *the organic protocol*, a mixture of zinc acetate (0.2M) and ethanolamine (0.5 equivalents) in methoxyethanol is reflux-heated at 90 °C for 3 h and filtered for subsequent deposition on the selected substrates. Deposition is conducted by spin-coating, for which the substrates, surface cleaned with ethanol, acetone and ultrasounds, are placed on the spin-coater holder and dripped with 3 drops of the freshly prepared zinc sol while rotating at 3000 rpm during 30 s. The as-deposited layer undergoes a sequential hot-plate drying process during short times for rapid evaporation of the solvent and decomposition/removal of the organic compounds; the specific temperature in the hot plates is determined by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). The whole process is repeated up to four times (4-layer film) and a last heating treatment is performed at 300 °C for 1 h to transform the gel into the oxide film, as defined also by TGA and XRD (Fig. S1). In the case of the aqueous solution-gel methodology, *the aqueous protocol*, the procedure involves some mandatory adaptations. The starting solution is produced by dissolving zinc citrate (0.2M) in presence of concentrated ammonia to assist in the formation of Zn^{2+} complexes. The evolution of the ammonium groups leads to the loss of the hygroscopic character of the material [28], and thus forces the consolidation of the deposited films to be conducted at higher temperatures, up to 500 °C (Fig. S2). On the other hand, substrates also require a surface hydrophilization treatment that increases their affinity for water and allows adequate adhesion of the solution during the spin-coating stage; the specific pre-treatment consist of immersing the substrate in a mixture of sulphuric acid and hydrogen peroxide for 1h (SPM Piranha etch, 4:1, H_2SO_4 , 95–97 %: H_2O_2 , 35 %). A schematic representation of both processing protocols is represented in Fig. 1.

2.3. Materials, equipment and characterization techniques

Zinc acetate ($\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 99+%, Aldrich) and zinc citrate ($\text{Zn}_3(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_7)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 97 %, Aldrich) di-hydrate reactants were distinctly used as the metal precursor source in the sol-gel and aqueous solution-gel protocols, respectively. 2-methoxyethanol (anhydrous, 99.8 %, Aldrich) was used as the solvent in the organic protocol, adjusting the viscosity of the solution with the controlled addition of

ethanolamine ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_7\text{NO}$, redistilled, 99.5+%, Aldrich). In the aqueous protocol distilled water is the only solvent and is supplemented with a concentrated ammonia solution (extra pure NH_3 , 32 % in H_2O , Merck). Substrates were purchased from Crystal GmbH and MTI Corporation. The deposition of the precursor sols was conducted with a spin-coating machine from Laurell Technologies.

Thermogravimetric analyses of the precursors were carried out in a TGA furnace of TA instruments, model 951–2000. TG analyses were carried out in air up to 600 °C with a heating ramp of 10 °C/min. The structural properties of parent substrates and the consolidated film samples were examined by X-ray diffraction using a XRD Bruker D500 machine. Patterns were collected on rotating samples between $2\theta = 15\text{--}70^\circ$, in steps of 0.05° and with a counting time of 1.5 s per step. Further structural differences within the films were investigated by grazing incidence diffraction analyses (GID) collected in the selected area between $2\theta = 30\text{--}40^\circ$; the GID data were taken for incidence angles of 1 and 2° , and reducing the step size to 0.015° . The morphology and microstructure of the ZnO thin films were investigated by field emission scanning electron microscopy (Cold FESEM Hitachi S-4700 microscope equipped with EDS probe). Film thickness, grain size and porosity measurements were taken directly from the FESEM micrographs using an image analyser program (Leica QWin). For the photocatalysis tests, the film samples on the different substrates are placed vertically in vials to which 5 mL of 10^{-6} M methyl orange (MO) solution is added. Blank tests with no light and no photocatalyst were first conducted as reference. The vials are irradiated with a System Photolab LED365-14/450-12c photoreactor (APRIA Systems S.L.) equipped with a $10 \times 10 \text{ cm}^2$ area irradiation cell, keeping the samples at a fixed distance of 20 cm from the lamp. The intensity of the LEDs in the UV-A range ($\lambda = 365\text{--}370 \text{ nm}$) was set to 100 %, and that of the LEDs in the Visible range ($\lambda = 400\text{--}700 \text{ nm}$) to 50 %. The degradation of the pollutant was followed by UV-Vis spectroscopy on aliquots of the solutions taken at a specific sequence of irradiation times. Quartz cuvettes with a width of 1 cm were used in a double beam spectrophotometer (Analytik - Jena Specord 200 plus) equipped with a deuterium lamp (UV region, range 190–318 nm) and a tungsten lamp (UV-Vis region, range 318–600 nm). The concentration of MO as a function of irradiation time was determined from the UV-Vis measurements. The degradation kinetics of methyl orange were evaluated by monitoring the concentration ratio (C/C_0) over time. The experimental data were fitted to a pseudo-first-order kinetic model using an exponential decay function. The calculated rate constants and the corresponding R^2 values for each experimental condition (method and substrate) are summarized in Table S1. Finally, the (internal) electronic band structure of the samples was analysed by solid state photoluminescence emission using a Spectrofluorometer FS5 from Edinburgh Instruments. The system is equipped with a Xe + UV lamp of 150W ($\lambda = 200\text{--}1000 \text{ nm}$) and integrating sphere, and the excitation

Fig. 1. Main steps in the two CSD protocols employed in this study to produce ZnO thin film coatings on selected substrates. The *organic* sol-gel procedure allows crystalline coatings to be obtained at temperatures as low as 300 °C, whereas 500 °C are needed in the *aqueous* solution-gel methodology for effective consolidation (as determined by XRD, see also Fig. S2). Note that substrates in the aqueous routine require a hydrophilization pre-treatment to ensure adhesion during spin coating deposition.

wavelength was fixed at 214 nm (bandwidth of 5 nm).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Silica glass substrates

Once the precursor sol has been dripped and centrifuged (spin-coating), the interaction of the as-deposited amorphous material with the substrate unit cells is key during subsequent nucleation and in the early stages of film growth. This largely depends on the structural compatibility between the substrate and the film upon heating. On silica glass substrates, the absence of long-range crystallographic order initially hinders the development of (hetero)epitaxial relationships with wurtzite ZnO, but still uniform deposits of good crystal quality can be attained. Fig. 2 summarizes the structural characterization of the thin films coating the glass substrates as produced by the *organic protocol*. At the 300 °C that we apply in this routine to consolidate the films, the XRD measurements detect the presence of polycrystalline peaks that weakly superpose to the diffuse scattering halo of the amorphous glass substrate. The angular positions are in agreement with the three main crystallographic orientations of the hexagonal structure of wurtzite ZnO: (10-10), (0002) and (10-11) reflections (Miller-Bravais notation), and a straight comparison of the Bragg intensities with the reference I_{hkl}^0 intensities in the crystallographic file ICDD 96-230-0451 initially suggests that no crystal direction has developed preferentially [38]. Grazing incidence X-ray diffraction (GID) analyses however provide no additional information for this sample, as no ZnO-related signals were detected at either 1° or 2° incidence angles (Fig. S3a), likely due to the low crystallinity of the organic-derived films. FESEM images on the other hand reveal a flat and homogeneous surface of the crystallized films which well reflects that of the substrate. The high magnification micrographs show the granular nature of the films; with an irregular to spherical morphology, the ZnO grains are closely packed without leading to crystal coarsening, which can be attributed to the low-temperature growth. The average thickness of the films reaches 135 nm with a grain size in the order of 20 nm, and at no time is it possible to distinguish the 4 deposited layers confirming the effectiveness of the consolidation treatment in densifying the films. The top view SEM

images ratify the grain size values, further exposing some common microstructural features on the surface of the sol-gel processed films. There is first the presence of what seems a wavelike topography (Fig. 2e), faintly perceptible in the cross-sectional images, and which some authors tag as a fibrous-type or wrinkled structure when it is more prominent [3,20,39]. Initially, associated with the relaxation of the compressive stress generated by the difference in the coefficients of thermal expansion between the substrate and the ceramic film, several factors can contribute to its more or less pronounced formation, such as the specific conditions of the heat treatment (heating/cooling) or the use of stabilizing (chelating) additives of given viscosity such as ethanolamine [20,40]. And directly related is the porosity observed between the nanocrystalline grains on the film surface, Fig. 2f. With an average value around 7–8 %, it is also a surface level condition, not interconnected through the film profile (as the cross-sectional images indicate), which is not affecting the closely packed structure of the films. Its origin is attributed to diffusion and coalescence processes between neighbouring grains as a result of thermal energy input [41], so it can be regulated by adjusting the annealing temperature, the amount of material (number of layers deposited), and other processing variables. Nevertheless, surface porosity also provides a higher surface-to-volume ratio in the exposed material that may benefit applications. For example, it has been found that ZnO films consisting of a porous structure formed by tightly packed nanocrystallites display improved sensing performance in gas detection processes [42]; likewise, it has been reported that porosity and even the observed wrinkling of the film surface can enhance the photocatalytic activity towards pollutant degradation, as both eventually lead to an increase in the effective exposed area (e.g. as compared to a dense, flat surface) [20].

When switching to the *aqueous protocol*, the first thing that is observed is a slight increase in the crystallinity of the ZnO films, as the corresponding XRD peaks now show higher intensity with respect to the baseline, Fig. 3a; this goes especially for the (0002) peak and so speaks of a certain preferential orientation in the c-axis direction. The oriented growth may be induced by the underlying substrate [17], but it can also respond to the strong tendency of ZnO to develop its c-plane: lower surface free energy of the (0001) plane caused by the sp^3 hybridized orbitals [43]. In any case, the overall structural improvement of these

Fig. 2. ZnO thin films produced by the organic sol-gel protocol on glass substrates. a) XRD pattern of the consolidated films revealing the presence of ZnO diffraction maxima with no preferential orientation (ICDD file n° 96-230-0451). b) XRD pattern of the raw glass substrate. c, d) Cross-sectional FESEM micrographs. e-g) Top-view FESEM images showing a wave-like topography.

Fig. 3. ZnO thin films deposited on glass substrates using the aqueous solution-gel protocol. a) XRD pattern of the consolidated films indicating some degree of orientation in the (0002) plane of the ZnO wurtzite network (ICDD file n° 96-230-0451). b, c) Cross-sectional and d, e) top-view FESEM images. f) EDX retrieved from the upper surface of the films.

aqueous processed films can be ascribed to the increase in crystallization temperature, 500 °C versus 300 °C in the organic protocol. Furthermore, the enhanced crystallinity achieved with the aqueous method is also evident in the GID analysis, as ZnO diffraction signals can now be detected at an incidence angle of 2° (Fig. S4a). Interestingly, the strong preferential orientation detected in the standard XRD measurements (Fig. 3a) is not replicated in the GID patterns (Fig. S4a). This situation can be interpreted by considering that grazing incidence geometry primarily analyses the uppermost regions of the film, i.e., the areas farthest from the substrate interface, where the influence of substrate-induced strain or crystallographic mismatch is minor. In a way, it suggests the presence of an orientation gradient within the film as we move away from the substrate, although the fact that such orientation feature is better observed in the standard XRD patterns also indicates that a significant portion of the film is indeed influenced by substrate effects. On the other hand, the FESEM cross-sectional inspection first shows strongly cohesive films of lower thickness (around 100 nm, increased coalescence), while the top view images confirm a finer microstructure with less surface porosity around 5 % (compare Fig. 2f/2g with Fig. 3d/3e) and an average size of the ZnO grains that yet remains in low values despite the temperature increase: 25 nm vs. 20 nm of the sol-gel processed films. Also, it should be noted that the wave-like structure observed on the surface of the films processed with the organic routine is not reproduced in the aqueous protocol, indicating a predominant role of ethanolamine in the surface wrinkling of our samples. Finally, the EDX spectrum shown in Fig. 3f confirms the expected presence of the deposited zinc on the glass substrate.

3.2. (0001)-oriented SiO₂ substrates

For device applications, a preferential orientation of the deposited films can be a crucial aspect determining the final properties of the system. As films tend to grow with a reproducible orientation relationship to the substrate, the use of well-crystallized substrates can help to promote a specific orientation. It implies that the relative differences between the comparable lattice dimensions of the deposited layer and the host substrate are reasonably close, so no large mismatch of lattice parameters will lead to excess strain at the interface. This may be the case when ZnO films are deposited on crystalline SiO₂, the most common

dielectric medium in integrated circuits. The trigonal symmetry of quartz SiO₂ in principle favours the growth of hexagonal ZnO with c-axis orientation perpendicular to the substrate, however, the specialized literature presents some disparity of results in this respect. For example, Chebil et al. attained remarkable epitaxial growth using a sol-gel plus spin-coating process similar to the one used here, although growing a 20-layer film which needs to be consolidated at temperatures as high as 1000 °C [44]. Puthiyottil et al. instead observed a much less prominent (0002) orientation in films deposited by RF magnetron sputtering (substrate heated at 450–700 °C) [45]. Here we deal with a (0001)-oriented silica substrate and the results obtained rather resemble those of the second scenario. This is shown by the images in Fig. 4, corresponding to the films produced by the *organic protocol*: while the XRD analysis evidences the absence of preferential orientation (also not seen by GID analyses, Fig. S3b), the FESEM inspection reveals uniform ZnO coatings with the same thickness, grain size and porosity values as the films deposited on the amorphous glass substrate. We seem to have a negligible induction effect of the crystalline SiO₂ substrate that also extends to the *aqueous protocol*, where the data in Fig. 5 practically reproduce those obtained with the same processing on an amorphous glass substrate (Fig. 3). Same thickness, same grain size and microstructural appearance, and also similar XRD patterns: the increase in the consolidation temperature when switching from the organic protocol to the aqueous treatment (from 300 to 500 °C), leads to an increase of the relative intensity of peak (0002) whose magnitude is, however, practically the same for the films deposited on the amorphous substrate and those obtained on quartz, see Fig. 5b. Fig. S4b And Fig. S4b with the corresponding GID analyses also resembles what was seen with the glass substrates: possible existence of an orientation gradient across the film (in this case visible already at a 1° angle of incidence). In other words, the higher thermal energy input in the aqueous routine impels the atoms to diffuse and occupy the most favourable sites within the ZnO crystal lattice (those that minimize the (0001) surface, i.e. growth in the c-direction), but at no time does the scaling in the crystallinity of the silica substrates make such preferential growth to be more pronounced. Some other authors have found a similar scenario when dealing with ZnO films and SiO₂ substrates, and for example Chakrabarti and co-workers even observed a higher orientation on amorphous glass in a process that they related to the presence of non-bridging oxygen atoms on its surface [46].

Fig. 4. ZnO thin films produced by the organic sol-gel protocol on (0001)-oriented quartz substrates. a) XRD pattern of the consolidated films and b) the parent quartz substrate (ICDD file n° 96-153-2513). c, d) Cross-sectional FESEM images and e-g) top-view micrographs showing again the wavy topography on the upper surface of the films.

Fig. 5. ZnO thin films deposited on quartz substrates using the aqueous solution-gel protocol. a) XRD pattern of the consolidated films. b) Comparison of the crystallinity of the films deposited on both quartz and amorphous glass substrates (normalised XRD), showing the same degree of preferential orientation (0002 plane). c, d) Cross-sectional and e, f) top-view FESEM images of the films deposited on crystalline quartz.

Linked, one way or another, to a distinctive property of SiO₂, the situation is likely to differ when depositing the ZnO films on other substrates.

3.3. Al₂O₃ substrates

As with silica substrates, oriented sapphire substrates have been considered to obtain ZnO thin films of high crystal quality, even though

the large in-plane mismatch of c-plane Al₂O₃ with the wurtzite lattice structure (in between 18 and 32 % depending on the rotating domains) [47] is a major impediment for heteroepitaxial growth. In this work we however use the alumina substrates to test the feasibility of the CSD processes in depositing films with a high degree of conformal coverage. Conformality has become an increasingly important characteristic in the fabrication of ceramic coatings as it enables for film properties to be optimized independently from the choice of the bulk material and shape

of the substrate [48]. On this basis we have selected a crystalline, not preferentially oriented, alumina substrate with a heterogeneous microstructure featuring irregularly shaped grains across a broad size distribution and displaying significant surface roughness (peak values reaching 1–2 μm), see Fig. 6a. The aim is to determine to what extent the films deposited using both the organic and the aqueous methodologies replicate or enhance the existing surface irregularities (including high aspect ratio features and 3D geometries) and to assess the impact on the film's structure. Starting with the *organic protocol*, the top view SEM images in Fig. 6c and d suggest that the ZnO coating obtained (as identified by EDS and XRD) fully reflects the topography of the alumina substrate. Increasing magnification shows that the Al_2O_3 grains are indeed covered by a uniform layer of ZnO grains, but it is also observed that this uniformity is lost at the grain boundaries and especially at the triple points and areas of higher relief between Al_2O_3 grains. In these regions the ZnO develops what looks like a fibrillary type structure that bridges the underlying topography of the substrate, Fig. 6f and g, thereby cancelling the possibility of obtaining a conformal deposition with this protocol. The formation of these structures can be linked to variations in the nucleation process of the films, which, in turn, may be caused by significant differences in the topography of the substrate. For example, working with vapour-deposited thin films, Unni et al. have recently observed that substrates with high surface roughness values can enhance heterogeneous nucleation at sites with an irregular surface [49]. It can even accelerate crystallization dynamics, eventually causing local grain growth. This is best observed in the film samples obtained by the *aqueous protocol* whose characterization is depicted in Fig. 7. The temperature increase associated with this processing routine again

causes an increase in the crystallinity of the films, although without leading to preferential orientation due to the aforementioned lattice mismatch between alumina and wurtzite (Fig. 7a). The FESEM micrographs indicate the presence of a thin ZnO layer on the flatter surface of the alumina grains, but now the fibrillary structures at the grain boundaries and triple points are no longer observed. Instead, the ZnO grains covering these regions exhibit a larger size than elsewhere in the film: image analyses retrieve around 60 nm in A-crest regions versus 25 nm in B-valley regions, confirming a preferential growth of the existing nuclei over the formation of new nuclei in these irregular zones of the substrate. The cross-sectional image of the samples further reveals the poor uniformity of the attained films, see Fig. 8: replicating the substrate's topography, thin coatings are obtained in ridge areas (A in Fig. 7) while significant deposits accumulate in valleys or depressions between alumina grains (B in Fig. 7). It is in the latter where the increased amount of material enhances the growth of the ZnO grains, leading to a heterogeneous microstructure that could affect the functional properties and may ultimately fail to meet the performance requirements of the intended application.

3.4. Platinum substrates

The Pt-based substrate that we have used in this study comprises a multilayer configuration with nominal composition Pt/Ti/SiO₂/Si. In this configuration silicon is the supporting substrate and usually displays a (100) orientation. Its surface is thermally oxidized to create a 300 nm thick SiO₂ barrier that allows adhesion of subsequent layers, although a ~ 10 nm sputtered Ti (or TiO₂) interlayer between silica and platinum is

Fig. 6. ZnO thin films produced by the organic sol-gel protocol on rough alumina substrates. a) FESEM/XRD of the raw alumina substrate (ICDD file n° 96-100-0033). b) XRD pattern of the deposited ZnO films. c, d, e) FESEM images and EDX retrieved from the upper surface of the films. f, g) magnified micrographs showing the presence of fibrillary structures at grain boundaries and triple point regions.

Fig. 7. ZnO thin films deposited on alumina substrates using the aqueous solution-gel protocol. a) XRD pattern of the consolidated ZnO films b) FESEM images evidencing poor microstructural homogeneity (non-uniform grain size distribution) in the obtained ZnO coatings as a result of the large topographical differences in the substrate.

also necessary to prevent debonding. The conductive platinum is sputtered onto the Ti surface, typically at a thickness of 150–200 nm; this Pt-layer is polycrystalline in nature and is oriented in its (111) direction to further facilitate epitaxial growth [50]. Fig. S5 shows the XRD of the parent substrate and its FESEM appearance confirming a thickness of 170 nm for the platinum metal layer. As film substrates, these Pt-coated silicon wafers have several advantages, including good chemical stability, low resistance and good weldability (for electrical contacts). Moreover, at issue here, the Pt (111) surface also displays a low in-plane misfit of just 1.4 % with *c*-ZnO (it was as high as 30 % on SiO₂ surfaces), which can lead to ZnO films with excellent crystalline quality [35]. At this point, it is generally assumed that since the Pt layer is in direct contact with the ZnO and has a thickness comparable to that of the deposited thin films, the other components of the Pt-based substrate have a less significant influence on both the growth habit and the functional properties of the films [51]. With this in mind, Fig. 9 first shows the characterization of the ZnO films deposited on the Pt-based

substrates after applying the *organic protocol* (crystallization temperature 300 °C). The first thing that can be observed is that the diffraction maxima of ZnO in the corresponding XRD analyses are strongly masked by those of the substrate. This makes it difficult to infer whether there is a preferential orientation of the ZnO crystals. GID analysis could be informative in this regard; however, as noted with the other substrates the low crystallinity of the organic-derived films is even more pronounced in the uppermost region of the films, so once again, no ZnO signals were detected by GID measurements (Fig. S3c). On the other hand, the FESEM images reveal a uniform and homogeneous coating of ZnO on top of the platinum layer. Measurements in the image analyser indicate an average ZnO grain size smaller than in the previous cases, about 15 nm, a percentage of porosity around 7–8 %, and a thickness of the ZnO films around 90 nm (ZnO-Pt assembly: 260 nm, measured thickness of the Pt layer: 170 nm, Fig. S5). This thickness is also much lower than that achieved with silica substrates (130 nm) and a possible explanation can be found in the aforementioned low lattice misfit of the

Fig. 8. ZnO thin films deposited on alumina substrates using the aqueous solution-gel protocol. The FESEM images show the difficulties of the proposed CSD protocols in achieving adequate conformal coverage on high roughness substrates.

Fig. 9. ZnO thin films produced by the organic sol-gel protocol on Pt oriented substrates with low in-plane misfit with the ZnO wurtzite lattice. a) XRD pattern of the consolidated ZnO films. b, c) Cross-sectional and d, e) top-view FESEM images. f) EDX retrieved from the upper surface of the films.

platinum substrate with ZnO. That is, although *a priori* no significant epitaxial growth is detected, the greater dimensional similarity between the in-plane networks of ZnO and Pt (111) would be favouring a more ordered arrangement and a more effective compaction of the ZnO crystals. Gopalakrishnan et al. made a similar observation when comparing silica and alumina substrates showing a different degree of lattice mismatch with ZnO: the misfit is more pronounced on SiO₂, ca. 30% versus 18% on alumina, and resulted in thicker and less compacted ZnO films [52]. Nevertheless, parameters such as the consolidation temperature of the films also have a bearing on the attained thickness. This is confirmed when switching to the *aqueous protocol*, where the

increase of the crystallization temperature up to 500 °C leads to important differences with the organic protocol, see Fig. 10. The first major difference is in the XRD: although the substrate peaks still partially mask those of the ZnO films, the latter are now more perceptible and show an intensity of the maximum corresponding to the (0002) plane which is remarkably higher than the other two main zinc oxide reflections, Fig. 10a and b. We expected that this time such pronounced orientation would be evident in the GID measurements too, but once again these only confirmed the hypothesis of an orientation gradient within the deposited films, decreasing from the substrate interface outwards, Fig. S4c. In any case, the increase of the consolidation

Fig. 10. ZnO thin films deposited on (111)-oriented Pt substrates using the aqueous solution-gel methodology. a, b) XRD pattern of the consolidated ZnO films showing the extraordinary level of crystallographic orientation (0002 plane) that can be achieved with this processing protocol. c, d) Corresponding cross-sectional and e, f) top-view FESEM images.

temperature highlights the epitaxial growth of the ZnO films, promoted by the favourable lattice matching with the Pt layer (it was not detected in the organic processed films, as they are crystallized at 300 °C). Interestingly, this results in thicker ZnO films, with values now around 160 nm (ZnO-Pt assembly: 330 nm), which thus reverse the trend observed with silicon substrates. What happens is that the suitable lattice matching between the oriented Pt and the wurtzite cell now also affects the growth habit of the ZnO structures, being more favoured in the c-axis than in any other direction of the hexagonal lattice (as confirmed by that exaggerated peak (0002) in the XRD, Fig. 10b); this causes the ZnO grains to grow mostly in height and, in the aqueous protocol, with the implied temperature increase, it eventually results in thicker films, Fig. 10c and d. Actually, we could anticipate a rod-like morphology in the crystallized ZnO grains. However, this is not evident in the FESEM images; while Pt columns are visible, it is likely that higher temperatures and/or additional material are needed for the rod morphology to show up in these ZnO films [38]. The top view images on the other hand confirm the increase in grain size (20 nm) and the decrease in porosity (5 %) that accompany the higher processing temperature of the aqueous processing, Fig. 10e and f. Regardless, the preferential growth along the c-axis will undoubtedly influence the photocatalytic performance of the films, and is discussed next.

3.5. Photocatalytic properties

As described in the experimental section, the photocatalytic response of the fabricated ZnO coatings was evaluated for the photodegradation of the standard methyl orange (MO) dye molecule. Samples on the alumina substrates had to be disregarded as they resulted in poorly reproducible measurements; this is attributed to the observed lack of microstructural homogeneity of the obtained ZnO deposits and the inadequate conformal coverage when using the two CSD proposed protocols with such a high roughness substrate. Photocatalysis experiments began with two control tests, Fig. S6. In the first, a vial containing 5 mL of a 10^{-6} M MO solution was irradiated for 24 h under the same conditions used in the subsequent assays. After this period, the absorbance at the maximum wavelength (465 nm) showed an insignificant decrease, indicating negligible degradation of the pollutant in the

absence of a photocatalyst, Fig. S6a. Similarly, a dark control was conducted by immersing one of the photocatalytic samples (the ZnO film deposited on a Pt-based substrate prepared via the organic method) in the MO solution without light exposure. Once again, change in absorbance was detected at the end of the test, confirming no pollutant degradation in the absence of light, Fig. S6b. With this in mind, Fig. 11 shows the results of the photocatalytic degradation of methyl orange with the ZnO thin films deposited on silica- and platinum-based substrates. The first two figures illustrate the concentration ratio of dye-degradation, C/C_0 , as determined by quantifying the change in absorbance of the MO characteristic absorption wavelength (465 nm) with the irradiation time [53]. The data were fitted using an exponential decay function, Table S1, which confirmed that the degradation process follows a first-order kinetic mechanism. In all cases, the complete degradation of the dye is achieved after 24 h of exposure, and at no time is the decomposition reaction stopped (the corresponding adsorption spectra indicated that no intermediate compounds or secondary species are formed that may passivate the catalyst surface). The plotted curves also suggest that the degradation rate varies in between samples. This is best seen in the Table attached in Fig. 11, which reveals that the photocatalytic activity of the ZnO coatings is strongly conditioned by the processing protocol, always faster in the films produced by the organic sol-gel methodology, as well as by the substrate on which the films are deposited, the most effective being the platinum-based substrates. The first condition is actually a faithful reflection of the level of crystallographic orientation that is achieved under each protocol: as described, in the aqueous processing the increase in crystallization temperature causes a preferential orientation of the ZnO crystals in the (0002) plane. It occurs to a greater or lesser extent with all the substrates tested (lattice mismatch depending, as the XRD data showed) and causes anisotropic crystal growth projected along the c-axis. Given the hexagonal structure of the ZnO wurtzite, this actually results in a lower density of polar (0001) faces exposed to the surrounding medium, Fig. 11c. At this respect, it should be stressed that heterogeneous photocatalysis on semiconducting ZnO is primarily a surface-based phenomenon that is highly sensitive to the exposed crystallographic planes: specifically, several studies have confirmed that the (0001) face of ZnO is the most photoactive in this oxide [54,55], which would explain the lower

Fig. 11. Evaluation of the photocatalytic activity (methyl orange degradation) of ZnO films produced by CSD methods on different substrates. a, b) Decrease of the pollutant concentration as a function of the irradiation time for the different samples produced. c) Exposure of the (0001) face of ZnO in different morphological scenarios. d) PL measurements retrieved from the ZnO films deposited on the different substrates. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

photocatalytic performance (slower degradation) of the films produced by the aqueous solution-gel protocol. By contrast, those obtained by the organic sol-gel process, with a less oriented growth and a more comparable exposure of all faces, including (0001), result in a more efficient photocatalysis. The other relevant difference in the Table in Fig. 11 concerns the type of substrate, with platinum-based substrates rendering faster MO decomposition. Here the different behaviour of the substrates is explained by the photodegradation mechanism itself as driven by the semiconductor catalyst. This mechanism is mainly governed by the capacity of photogenerated charge carriers to reach the surface of ZnO, where they react either directly and/or with small adsorbed molecules to form reactive radicals ($\bullet\text{OH}$ and $\bullet\text{O}_2^-$) that decompose the organic dye [55]. In the overall process, one of the major impediments directly affecting performance is the recombination of electron-hole pairs (excitons) which rapidly reduces the quantum efficiency of the photocatalytic reaction [56]. In order to increase the lifetime of the photogenerated excitons, several strategies have been implemented, including the formation of semiconductor-semiconductor or metal-semiconductor heterojunctions, as these can favour a more effective segregation (migration) of the charge carriers. In our case, the deposition of ZnO on the Pt (111) surface generates a Schottky-type heterojunction which as a result of locally generated electric fields can promote the migration of the charge carriers in the direction of particular destinations, thus reducing their recombination and increasing the photocatalytic rate [57]. We have verified this scenario by photoluminescence (PL) measurements which allow an estimation of the magnitude of the recombination processes. When semiconducting ZnO is irradiated with photons with a frequency higher than the bandgap (excitation wavelength = 214 nm in our case), different

phenomena can occur, namely the photogeneration of free excitons which can subsequently recombine radiatively giving rise to the PL spectrum [58]. Depending on the excitation wavelength, different PL emissions can be detected, being frequent to observe a near to the band edge (NBE) emission falling around the UV region. This NBE emission originates from the excitonic transitions between electrons and holes in the conduction band and the valence band, and its intensity can be linked to the amount of recombination processes occurring in the ZnO lattice: the PL intensity drops when the amount of electron-hole recombinations is reduced [59,60]. With this in mind, Fig. 11d depicts the photoluminescence measurements retrieved from the ZnO films deposited on the different substrates. In all cases, a broad emission band centred in the near-visible UV region is recorded, with a substantial reduction in PL intensity for the films deposited on platinum. The PL quenching is not accompanied by relevant changes in the peak position or the overall band shape (which could be indicative of the presence of different trap states or the generation of new surface defects [58,61]), so it can be associated with a lower recombination rate of the photo-generated electrons and holes. These measurements therefore confirm that the direct contact between ZnO and Pt generates a functional heterojunction that allows electron transfer to take place between their respective energy levels, which translates into a higher separation efficiency and, eventually, a better photocatalytic response.

Finally, it should be noted that the photocatalytic performance ultimately depends on a combination of several factors beyond the processing protocol and the specific substrate. But in any case, the results achieved with these films processed by CSD routes are at the same level or even improve those obtained in recent studies with thin films produced by more sophisticated and energy-intensive methods. For

example, dealing with ZnO films produced by PLD, Koruda et al. need 10 h to achieve a MO dye degradation of about 45 % [43]; similarly Prucnal et al. have seen yields of 60 % in the first 3–4 h operating in this case with TiO₂ films produced by reactive magnetron sputtering, but they also find that degradation slows down after 6 h due to unwanted passivation of the catalyst surface during the decomposition of the MO molecule [62].

4. Conclusions

This work presents novel insights into the fabrication of functional (photocatalytic) ZnO ceramic coatings using chemical solution deposition (CSD) techniques, specifically sol-gel and the less explored aqueous solution-gel methodologies. In the context of developing more sustainable manufacturing processes, our findings underscore the viability of CSD as a low-cost, low-impact alternative to traditional vapour-phase deposition techniques. A key innovation of this work lies in the demonstration that the aqueous method—not only environmentally superior due to the absence of alcohol and toxic additives—consistently enhances the crystallinity of the resulting ZnO films. This improvement proves critical, as it can enable epitaxial-like growth on selected substrates, a feature rarely reported for such low-temperature, solution-based approaches. This positions the aqueous route as a compelling alternative for high-quality film growth with a significantly reduced environmental footprint. Equally unprecedented is the observation that both sol-gel and aqueous solution-gel films exhibit a preferential orientation gradient, decreasing from the substrate interface to the film surface. This structural feature suggests a self-organization mechanism driven by interfacial interactions and film evolution, opening new avenues for tuning film orientation through process design (something not previously reported for CSD-processed films). While the versatility of both methods allows for deposition on a variety of substrates, this work also highlights critical limitations, particularly when dealing with substrates of high surface roughness, where achieving conformal coverage remains a challenge. As far as photocatalytic response is concerned, platinum-based substrates significantly enhance performance, likely through formation of a functional heterostructures that reduces electron-hole recombination and improves photocatalytic efficiency. Although further optimization is needed (in the particular case of photocatalytic functionality by doping, incorporating growth directional agents or even by increasing the porosity of the films) this study provides strong evidence that CSD techniques can be refined to meet demanding application requirements. The combination of enhanced film properties, sustainability, and scalability makes them highly attractive for future technological deployment. Overall, this work not only validates the potential of CSD methods for fabricating high-performance ZnO thin films but also introduces new structural and functional insights that expand the current understanding of solution-based thin-film processing. Continued research should aim to fine-tune solution chemistry and deposition parameters, especially for challenging substrate topographies, ultimately positioning CSD as a key technology for the sustainable production of advanced ceramic coatings.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Laura San-Miguel: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation. **Ana Castellanos-Aliaga:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Investigation. **Rodrigo Codrón:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **David G. Calatayud:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Ángel Caballero:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Carlos Gumiel:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Amador C. Caballero:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Teresa Jardiel:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Marco Peiteado:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision,

Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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References

- [1] S. Vyas, A short review on properties and applications of zinc oxide based thin films and devices, *Johnson Matthey Technol. Rev.* 64 (2020) 202–218, <https://doi.org/10.1595/205651320X15694993568524>.
- [2] J.K. Saha, J. Jang, Saturation mobility of 100 cm² V⁻¹ s⁻¹ in ZnO thin-film transistors through quantum confinement by a nanoscale In₂O₃ interlayer using spray pyrolysis, *ACS Nano* 18 (2024) 30484–30496, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.4c08644>.
- [3] S.S. Bhat, S.J. Shetty, M.P. Shilpa, S. Shet, K.M. Eshwarappa, S.C. Gurumurthy, Neutron irradiation induced transmuted Ga-doping of ZnO thin films: structural and opto-electronic investigations, *Ceram. Int.* 51 (2025) 2695–2700, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2024.11.252>.
- [4] A.H. Haritha, M. Rozam, A. Duran, D. Galusek, J.J. Velázquez, Y. Castro, Sol-gel derived ZnO thin film as a transparent counter electrode for WO₃ based electrochromic devices, *Bol. Soc. Esp. Ceram. V* 63 (2024) 135–144, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bsecev.2023.08.002>.
- [5] M.A. De la Rubia, M. Peiteado, J.F. Fernández, A.C. Caballero, J. Holc, S. Drnovsek, D. Kuscer, S. Macek, M. Kosec, Thick film ZnO based varistors prepared by screen printing, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 26 (2006) 2985–2989, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2006.02.016>.
- [6] T.R. Acharya, D.K. Chaudhary, P. Lamichhane, S.K. Joshi, S. Gautam, N. Kaushik, A.A. Al-Khedhairi, R. Wahab, M.B. Singh, P. Singh, E.H. Choi, N.K. Kaushik, Impact of aluminum doping on the enhanced ethanol gas sensing characteristics of ZnO thin film, *Ceram. Int.* 50 (2025) 55143–55158, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2024.10.364>.
- [7] A. Atilgan, K. Ozel, M. Sbeta, A. Yildiz, Engineering the visible light absorption of one-dimensional photonic crystals based on multilayers of Al-doped ZnO (AZO) thin films, *Mater. Sci. Semicond. Proc.* 166 (2023) 107747, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mssp.2023.107747>.
- [8] B. Aydas, A. Atilgan, A. Ajjaq, A. Acar, M.F. Ötkem, A. Yildiz, Flexible NH₃ gas sensors based on ZnO nanostructures deposited on kevlar substrates via hydrothermal method, *Ceram. Int.* 50 (2024) 32477–32489, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2024.06.056>.
- [9] R. Jalal, K. Ozel, A. Atilgan, A. Yildiz, UV photodetectors based on W-doped ZnO thin films, *Nanotechnology* 35 (2024) 265705, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6528/ad373b>.
- [10] W. Vallejo, A. Cantillo, C. Díaz-Urbe, Improvement of the photocatalytic activity of ZnO thin films doped with manganese, *Heliyon* 9 (2023) e20809, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e20809>.
- [11] J. Paniagua-Méndez, S.L. Ramírez-Sandoval, E. Reyes-Urbe, M.E. Contreras-García, Photocatalytic activity and biocide effect of nanostructured SnO₂/ZnO/TiO₂ thin film heterostructure obtained by sol-gel spin coating technique, *Ceram. Int.* 50 (2024) 34421–34430, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2024.06.261>.
- [12] Y.A. Volkovskiy, V.A. Zhernova, M.S. Folomeshkin, P.A. Prodsekov, A.E. Muslimov, A.V. Butashin, A.M. Ismailov, Y.V. Grigoriev, Y.V. Pisarexkym, V.M. Kanevsky, Comparative X-ray diffractometry of the defect structure of ZnO epitaxial films deposited by magnetron sputtering on c-plane Al₂O₃ substrates in inhomogeneous electric field, *Crystallogr. Rep.* 68 (2023) 195–202, <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1063774523020219>.

- [13] A.M. Olteanu, A.I. Nicoara, V.A. Surdu, G.O. Isopencu, D.D. Banciu, S.I. Jinga, C. Busuioic, I. Constantinou, Antibacterial activity of tin-doped zinc oxide thin films deposited by laser ablation, *Ceram. Int.* 50 (2024) 3497–3510, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2023.11.098>.
- [14] J.K. Ahn, S.J. Oh, H. Park, Y. Song, S.J. Kwon, H.B. Shin, Vapor-phase deposition-based self-assembled monolayer for an electrochemical sensing platform, *AIP Adv.* 10 (2020) 045213, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5144845>.
- [15] U. Chaitra, D. Kekuda, K.M. Rao, Effect of annealing temperature on the evolution of structural, microstructural, and optical properties of spin coated ZnO thin films, *Ceram. Int.* 43 (2017) 7115–7122, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2017.02.144>.
- [16] L. Qi, M. Babar-Shahzad, Y. Qi, A reproducible low temperature chemical solution deposition of non-polar [11-20] and [10-10] ZnO films for optoelectronic applications, *CrystEngComm* 18 (2016) 6573–6578, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C6CE01054G>.
- [17] X. Meng, B. Zhang, L. xu, N. Khadija, G. Fan, Y. Zhou, H. Liu, F. Xu, Contribution of Li substitution for Zn to green light emission of ZnO ceramic thin films, *Ceram. Int.* 50 (2024) 16046–16050, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2024.02.083>.
- [18] S. Hiromoto, Chemical solution deposition of hydroxyapatite and octacalcium phosphate coatings for magnesium and its alloys to improve biocompatibility, in: *Surface Modification of Magnesium and its Alloys for Biomedical Applications*, Woodhead Publishing Series in Biomaterials, 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-1-78242-078-1.00003-7>.
- [19] L. Znaidi, Sol-gel-deposited ZnO thin films: a review, *Mater. Sci. Eng. B* 174 (2010) 18–30, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mseb.2010.07.001>.
- [20] E.A. Daher, B. Riachi, J. Cahmoun, C. Laberty-Robert, W. Hamd, New approach for designing wrinkled and porous ZnO thin films for photocatalytic applications, *Colloid Surf. A-Physicochem. Eng. Asp.* 658 (2023) 130628, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfa.2022.130628>.
- [21] R. Gegová-Dzhurkova, D. Nesheva, I. Stambolova, K. Zaharieva, V. Dzhurkov, I. Miloushev, Enhanced photocatalytic performance under ultraviolet and visible light illumination of ZnO thin films prepared by modified sol-gel method, *Molecules* 29 (2024) 4005, <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules29174005>.
- [22] K.M. Sandeep, S. Bhat, P. Kumar, U. Vinoditha, S.M. Dharmaprakash, Polar axis oriented crystal growth induced carrier transport characteristics in non-degenerate zinc oxide thin films grown on glass substrates, *Ceram. Int.* 45 (2019) 16631–16637, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2019.05.204>.
- [23] T. Saidani, M. Zaabat, M.S. Aida, R. Barille, M. Rasheed, Y. Almohamed, Influence of precursor source on sol-gel deposited ZnO thin films properties, *J. Mater. Sci. Mater. Electron.* 28 (2017) 9252–92571, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10854-017-6660-9>.
- [24] B. Joos, K. Elen, J. van den Ham, N. Meulendijks, P. Buskens, A. Paulus, K. Wouters, J. Manca, J. D'Haen, S. Shukla, B. Vermag, M. Van Bael, A. Hardy, Facile aqueous solution-gel route toward thin film CuBi_2O_4 photocathodes for solar hydrogen production, *Adv. Sust. Systems* 7 (2023) 2300083, <https://doi.org/10.1002/advs.202300083>.
- [25] A. Hardy, J. D'Haen, L. Goux, K. Wouters, M.K. Van Bael, H. van den Rul, J. Mullens, Aqueous chemical solution deposition of ferroelectric Ti^{++} Co-substituted $(\text{Bi},\text{La})_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$ thin films, *Chem. Mater.* 19 (2007) 2994–3001, <https://doi.org/10.1021/cm070101x>.
- [26] T. Vranken, W. Van Gompel, J. D'Haen, M.K. Van Bael, A. Hardy, Aqueous solution-gel precursors for LiFePO_4 lithium ion battery cathodes, their decomposition and phase formation, *J. Sol. Gel Sci. Technol.* 84 (2017) 198–205, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10971-017-4467-z>.
- [27] C. Gumiel, T. Jardiel, D.G. Calatayud, T. Vranken, M.K. Van Bael, A. Hardy, M. L. Calzada, R. Jiménez, M. García-Hernández, F.J. Mompeán, A.C. Caballero, M. Peiteado, Nanostructure stabilization by low-temperature dopant pinning in multiferroic BiFeO_3 -based thin films produced by aqueous chemical solution deposition, *J. Mater. Chem. C* 8 (2020) 4234–4245, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9TC05912A>.
- [28] D. Mondelaers, G. Vanhoyland, H. van den Rul, J. D'Haen, M.K. van Bael, J. Mullens, L.C. van Poucke, Chemical solution deposition of ZnO thin films by an aqueous solution gel precursor route, *J. Sol. Gel Sci. Technol.* 26 (2003) 523–526, <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1020703500515>.
- [29] H. Damm, P. Adriaenssens, C. De Dobbelaere, B. Capon, K. elem, J. Drijkoningen, B. Conings, J.V. Manca, J. D'Haen, C. Detavernier, P.C.M.M. Magusin, J. Hadermann, A. Hardy, M.K. Van Bael, Factors influencing the conductivity of aqueous solution-gel-processed Al-doped ZnO films, *Chem. Mater.* 26 (2014) 5839–5851, <https://doi.org/10.1021/cm501820a>.
- [30] D.D. Le, T.S. Ngo, J.H. Song, S.K. Hong, Epitaxial growth of bandgap tunable ZnSn_2 films on (0001) Al_2O_3 substrates by using a ZnO buffer, *Cryst. Growth Des.* 18 (2018) 1385–1393, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.cgd.7b01285>.
- [31] J. Singh, S. Ranwa, J. Akhtar, M. Kumar, Growth of residual stress-free ZnO films on SiO_2/Si substrate at room temperature for MEMS devices, *AIP Adv.* 5 (2015) 067140, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4922911>.
- [32] K. Kaneko, T. Oga, S. Kaneko, T. Katase, M. Yoshimoto, A. Matsuda, Buffer-free epitaxial growth of ZnO(0001) thin films at room temperature by tetramethylammonium hydroxide pretreatment of a- Al_2O_3 (0001) substrates, *J. Ceram. Soc. Jpn.* 131 (2023) 383–388, <https://doi.org/10.2109/jcersj2.23022>.
- [33] L. Wen, L. Hu, Y. Qi, J. Zhou, W. Chen, Aqueous solution-gel preparation and dielectric properties of $\text{Ba}(\text{Mg}_{1/3}\text{Nb}_{2/3})\text{O}_3$ thin films with long-range order, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 98 (2015) 873–878, <https://doi.org/10.1111/jace.13367>.
- [34] C. Gumiel, T. Jardiel, A.P. Villalpando, D. Lamotte, D.G. Calatayud, M.L. Calzada, R. Jiménez, M. García-Hernández, F.J. Mompeán, A.C. Caballero, M. Villegas, M. Peiteado, Suppressing the non-switching contribution in $\text{BiFeO}_3\text{-Bi}_4\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_{12}$ based thin film composites to produce room-temperature multiferroic behaviour, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 42 (2022) 5615–5623, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2022.06.004>.
- [35] J.R. Duclère, C. Mc Loughlin, J. Fryar, R. O'Haire, M. Guilloux-Viry, A. Meaney, A. Perrin, E. McGlynn, M.O. Henry, J.P. Mosnier, ZnO thin films grown on platinum (111) buffer layers by pulsed laser deposition, *Thin Solid Films* 200 (2006) 78–83, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsf.2005.11.017>.
- [36] R. Serhane, S. Abdelli-Messaci, S. Lafane, H. Khales, W. Aouimeur, A. Hassen-Bey, T. Boutkedjirt, Pulsed laser deposition of piezoelectric ZnO thin films for bulk acoustic wave devices, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 288 (2014) 572–578, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2013.10.075>.
- [37] C. Gumiel, D.G. Calatayud, Thin film processing of multiferroic BiFeO_3 : from sophistication to simplicity. A review, *Bol. Soc. Esp. Ceram. V* 61 (2022) 708–732, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bsecv.2021.08.002>.
- [38] A. del Rocío López Guémez, A. Cordero García, J.L. Cervantes López, H. Pérez Vidal, L.L. Díaz Flores, Evaluation of the photocatalytic activity of ZnO nanorods and nanoflowers grown from seed layers deposited by spin coating, *Bol. Soc. Esp. Ceram. V* 63 (2024) 72–84, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bsecv.2023.06.003>.
- [39] D. Kim, J.Y. Leem, Optimal temperature of the sol-gel solution used to fabricate high-quality ZnO thin films via the dip-coating method for highly sensitive UV photodetectors, *J. Korean Phys. Soc.* 78 (2021) 504–509, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40042-021-00061-x>.
- [40] P. Ariyakkani, L. Suganya, B. Sundaresan, Investigation of the structural, optical and magnetic properties of Fe doped ZnO thin films coated on glass by sol-gel spin coating method, *J. Alloy. Compd.* 695 (2017), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2016.12.011>, 3467–347.
- [41] Y.C. Yoon, K.S. Park, S.D. Kim, Effects of low preheating temperature for ZnO seed layer deposited by sol-gel spin coating on the structural properties of hydrothermal ZnO nanorods, *Thin Solid Films* 597 (2015) 125–130, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsf.2015.11.040>.
- [42] N.B. Patil, A.R. Nimbalkar, M.G. Patil, ZnO thin film prepared by a sol-gel spin coating technique for NO_2 detection, *Mater. Sci. Eng. B* 227 (2018) 53–60, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mseb.2017.10.011>.
- [43] K. Koruda, K. Kaminaga, T. Tobe, S. Maruyama, Y. Matsumoto, NaCl flux growth of non-polar m-plane ZnO epitaxial thin film on c-plane sapphire substrate, *Thin Solid Films* 788 (2024) 140169, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsf.2023.140169>.
- [44] W. Chebil, M.A. Boukadhaha, A. Fouzi, Epitaxial growth of ZnO on quartz substrate by sol-gel spin-coating method, *Superlattices Microstruct.* 95 (2016) 48–55, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spmi.2016.04.033>.
- [45] H. Puthiyottil, P.R. Thankamani, K.J. Saji, Exploring the effects of substrate and substrate temperature on the properties of radio frequency magnetron sputtered ZnO thin films, *Mater. Today Commun.* 36 (2023) 106455, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtcomm.2023.106455>.
- [46] S. Chakarabarti, D. Ganguli, S. Chaudhuri, Substrate dependence of preferred orientation in sol-gel-derived zinc oxide films, *Mater. Lett.* 58 (2004) 3952–3957, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matlet.2004.09.002>.
- [47] T. Trautniz, R. Sorgenfrei, M. Fiederle, Elimination of rotation domains in ZnO thin films on c-plane Al_2O_3 substrates, *J. Cryst. Growth* 312 (2010) 624–627, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcrysgro.2009.12.011>.
- [48] P. Moni, A. Al-Obaidi, K.K. Gleason, Vapor deposition routes to conformal polymer thin films, *Beilstein J. Nanotechnol.* 8 (2017) 723–735, <https://doi.org/10.3762/bjnano.8.76>.
- [49] A. Beena Unni, R. Winkler, D.M. Duarte, K. Chat, K. Adrjanowicz, Influence of surface roughness on the dynamics and crystallization of vapor-deposited thin films, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 126 (2022) 8072–8079, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.2c04541>.
- [50] MIT corporation, materials for thin films. <https://mtixtl.com/collections/si-sio2-ti-tio2-pt-thin-film>. (Accessed 1 April 2025).
- [51] H. Yamada, Y. Ushimi, M. Takeuchi, Y. Yoshino, T. Makino, S. Arai, Improvement of crystallinity of ZnO thin film and electrical characteristics of film bulk acoustic wave resonator by using Pt buffer layer, *Vacuum* 74 (2004) 689–692, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vacuum.2004.01.061>.
- [52] N. Gopalakrishnan, L. Balakrishnan, K. Latha, S. Gowrishankar, Influence of substrate and film thickness on structural, optical and electrical properties of ZnO thin films, *Cryst. Res. Technol.* 46 (2011) 361–367, <https://doi.org/10.1002/crat.201100009>.
- [53] D.G. Calatayud, T. Jardiel, M. Peiteado, F. Illas, E. Giamello, F.J. Palomares, D. Fernández-Hevia, A.C. Caballero, Synthesis and characterization of blue faceted anatase nanoparticles through extensive fluorine lattice doping, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 119 (2015) 21243–21250, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.5b06923>.
- [54] E.S. Jang, J.H. Wong, S.J. Hwang, J.H. Choy, Fine tuning of the face orientation of ZnO crystals to optimize their photocatalytic activity, *Adv. Mater.* 18 (2006) 3309–3312, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.200601455>.
- [55] A. Baillard, E. Appert, L. Rapenne, V. Jacob, A. Dieulesaint, J.M. Chauveau, V. Consonni, Significance of the different exposed surfaces of ZnO single crystals and nanowires on the photocatalytic activity and processes, *Small Struct.* 5 (2024) 2300540, <https://doi.org/10.1002/ssr.202300540>.
- [56] D.G. Calatayud, R.M. Flores, A. Castellanos-Aliaga, M. Peiteado, F.J. Palomares, A.C. Caballero, T. Jardiel, Tailoring the visible light photoactivity of un-doped defective TiO_2 anatase nanoparticles through a simple two-step solvothermal process, *Nanotechnology* 31 (2020) 04560, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6528/ab49af>.
- [57] T.R. Sobahi, M.S. Amin, Synthesis of $\text{ZnO}/\text{ZnFe}_2\text{O}_4/\text{Pt}$ nanoparticles heterojunction photocatalysts with superior photocatalytic activity, *Ceram. Int.* 46 (2020) 3558–3564, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2019.10.073>.

- [58] J. Rodrigues, N. Ben Sedrine, M.R. Correia, T. Monteiro, Photoluminescence investigations of ZnO micro/nanostructures, *Mater. Chem. Today* 16 (2020) 100243, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtchem.2020.100243>.
- [59] B. Zeng, X. Ning, L. Li, Fabrication and photocatalytic performance of highly active exposed facets ZnO hexagonal cap/Ti₃C₂ MXene composites, *J. Alloy. Compd.* 963 (2023) 171309, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2023.171309>.
- [60] K.H. Prasad, S. Vinoth, V. Ganesh, R. Ade, I.S. Yahia, Enhanced photo-sensing activity of In-doped ZnO nanoparticles synthesized by wet chemical method, *Physica B* 678 (2024) 415710, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physb.2024.415710>.
- [61] B. Sarma, S.K. Deb, B.K. Sarma, Photoluminescence and photocatalytic activities of Ag/ZnO metal-semiconductor heterostructure, *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* 765 (2016) 012023, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/765/1/012023>.
- [62] S. Prucnal, R. Gago, D.G. Calatayud, L. Rebohle, M.O. Liedke, M. Butterling, A. Wagner, M. Helm, S. Zhou, TiO₂ phase engineering by millisecond range annealing for highly efficient photocatalysis, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 127 (2023) 12686–12694, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.3c01165>.